

PROSPECTS OF DIGITAL BANK DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract:

The article considers the prospects of digital bank development in Uzbekistan. In recent years, the banking industry has witnessed a significant transformation with the emergence of digital banks. These innovative financial institutions are revolutionizing the way we manage our money, making banking more accessible, convenient, and efficient.

Keywords: digital banking, FinTech, digital banking in Uzbekistan, Uzbek economists, Internet banking, cyber security

Looking at the current global economic situation, banking and financial systems are rapidly transforming. With the latest developments in information technology, business activities and financial organizations are changing as well. The growing accessibility of the internet and digital means of communication to all segments of the world's population makes it possible for many financial services not only to exist but also to grow and develop. Caring companies and institutions may become suppliers not only of information and services but also filter a customer's needs to improve cooperation and better service levels with the help of information obtained through this interface. Given the changes in consumer behaviour, interests, and complaints, banks are updating their service offerings to create added value for their customers. More and more countries around the world are undergoing digitization. The concept of "digital banks" is consolidating, and their emergence is expected in a number of countries soon. John Ginovsky describes digital banking as "the integration of new and evolving technologies in the activities of financial institutions with appropriate changes in internal and external corporate and personal relationships to expand customer service and increase the efficiency of banking. The analysis focuses on the prospects of further development and innovation in the sphere of digital banking in Uzbekistan. The sphere of financial activities today is the most digitalized. Clients have the possibility to manage bank accounts online. With Internet access, they can perform all the operations that are within the competence of the bank, whether it's everyday front-office functionalities, such as consultation on loan servicing, account balance consultation, or more complex back-office functionalities provided through the bank's official website, such as transferring funds from one account to another, including those opened with different banks, transferring funds to the account in the payment system, interbank operations, or simply payment for services provided through payment gateways.

The creation of a digital banking system is one of the key concerns since it will boost consumer trust in the system and provide practical services. According to research, a bank that offers banking services remotely or through a subsidiary is considered a digital bank if it uses cutting-edge banking technologies (without offering cash services). Digital banks should be considered as a set of software for online presentation of banking products to users of banking services. It is digital banking that should provide convenient banking services to customers (users). A.A. Gontar argues that “digital banking” is a new form of interaction between a bank and its customers, including innovations in the field of financial services for consumers and commercial clients in the field of digital, information and technology strategies”. In Uzbekistan, a lot of work is being done to promote initiatives for the development of digital banking services, the introduction of modern and advanced types of banking services, the introduction of new information technologies, increasing the popularity of banking services, its application in the banking market. Numerous studies on the evolution of digital transformation and the process of transformation in the banking industry were carried out by Uzbek economists. According to academician SS Gulomov, "new business models that integrate the digital and physical worlds are regarded as the emergence of digital business." Uzbekistan's financial system is evolving to meet the demands of the contemporary digital economy. Due to the digital transformation, business models and concepts for the development of the banking sector are being developed and improved; in particular, since the advent of Internet banking, innovative methods have been used to present traditional banking operations. As a result, through the innovative development of banks, their competitiveness and sustainable operation, efficiency, and most importantly, the growth of public confidence in the bank are being created.

According to a 2009 research by Ghosh and Ruziev, as the use of digital banking techniques grows, FinTech has greatly benefited Uzbekistan's banking industry. The country has recorded marked reductions in the number of physical branches, despite its operational costs being cut down on their magnitude with increased digitization in the delivery of banking services. In this, the number of physical brick-and-mortar branches located around the country has reduced, bringing about giant savings to these banks. Another way the banking sector has harnessed to ensure efficiency and productivity is the shift to digital banking channels. Automating processes and data processing in real time has optimized the operations of banks, meaning the banks can optimize their resources for improved service delivery. Digital banking further offers Uzbek banks leverage in advanced data analytics and customer insights.

Number of users of remote bank account services in the Republic of Uzbekistan

The diagram shows that as of April 1, 2019, 9,371,447 clients in the Republic of Uzbekistan were using remote management of bank accounts, with 498,936 being legal entities and individual entrepreneurs and 8,872,511 being individuals. However, business organizations visit a commercial bank to evaluate the relative worth of several remote banking services before deciding on one. Specifically, the high cost of the online banking system is recognized. After the bank begins providing services, the business entity is responsible for making sure that remote services are included in the service contract. It is then advisable to provide other service online and on a 24-basis.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, Uzbekistan's digital bank growth has a bright future ahead of it. The banking industry is at the vanguard of this transition as the nation embraces digital transformation and technical improvements. A strong digital banking ecosystem is made possible by the government's dedication to expanding financial inclusion and the growing population's use of digital technologies. To create a safe and effective digital banking environment, investments in cyber security, regulatory frameworks, and infrastructure are crucial. Collaboration between FinTech firms and traditional banks can also spur innovation by providing specialized services that cater to the wide range of customer needs. Digital banks may become more competitive by putting the customer experience first and using data analytics. In the end, the effective growth of digital banking in Uzbekistan would boost economic expansion, enhance the general standard of living for its people, and aid in the modernization of the financial industry. The potential for a thriving and inclusive digital banking environment is still substantial as Uzbekistan moves through this revolutionary process, establishing the country as a leader in the regional financial technology market.

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